

The Recovery of Sucrose from Cane-sugar Molasses.

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It is well known that a considerable quantity of sucrose remains in molasses, being prevented from crystallising by the presence of other substances. Sucrose is recovered on a commercial scale from beet-sugar molasses by precipitating the difficultly soluble strontium succinate, which is collected, washed and decomposed by carbonic acid, which precipitates strontium carbonate and liberates pure sucrose in solution; or more economically by the Steffen process which uses lime instead of strontia, and precipitates the difficultly soluble tricalcium succinate. In practice the tricalcium succinate is never decomposed by carbonic acid directly but is added to fresh juice, instead of its equivalent of lime, and is decomposed in the carbonation process, so that the sucrose recovered from the molasses is added to a following batch of juice. The authors have never seen any data as to the yield and purity of sucrose recoverable from beet-sugar molasses by the Steffen process. The authors are informed by Mr. Noel Deerr that in Europe nearly all sugar factories are equipped for the Steffen process and that whether the molasses is treated by this process or sold for the manufacture of cattle food depends on the relative prices of sugar and molasses at the time.

It is stated in the literature that cane-sugar molasses

cannot be treated by the Steffen process owing to the presence in it of a considerable quantity of invert sugar which would be decomposed by lime giving dark-coloured and troublesome decomposition products. One suggestion for the recovery of sucrose from cane-sugar molasses is to ferment it by a special yeast that acts on the invert sugar only, then to distil off the alcohol and recover sucrose from the spent wash by Steffen's process. Apparently there are yeasts which under carefully controlled conditions will ferment invert sugar and leave sucrose unattacked but it has not yet been possible to operate with these yeasts on a manufacturing scale.

Battelle's process (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1912, 31, 1195; 1915, 34, 916; 1919, 38, 784A) for manufacturing sugar from sugar-cane contains the essentials of a method for recovering sucrose from cane sugar molasses. In this process the juice is heavily limed and subjected to a vigorous boil which decomposes invert sugar in the juice with production of colourless or light coloured substances instead of those dark-coloured products obtained by the action of lime at lower temperatures. The juice is then carbonated, etc., as in the ordinary process for manufacturing sugar and the molasses left, after the sugar has crystallised, is like beet-sugar molasses in character (since it contains no appreciable quantity of invert sugar) and is treated by Steffen's process.

Battelle's process has been given a trial on a large scale. Undoubtedly it gives a larger yield of sugar from the juice but the increase of yield has not been considered sufficient to justify the additional plant and treatment necessary.

With slight modification the process would seem to be suitable for the recovery of sucrose from cane-sugar molasses as a process by itself, *viz.*, by diluting the molasses and boiling with lime to destroy the invert

sugar, then precipitating the sucrose as tricalcium sucrate filtering and treating with carbonic acid to liberate sucrose. The present investigation is an examination of this process.

PRELIMINARY EXPERIMENTS

(PERFORMED BY THE LATE D. N. GUPTA.)

Precipitation of Sucrose by Lime.

It appears that it is necessary to use freshly burnt lime in a finely ground condition and to stir this gradually into the cooled sucrose solution in order to get a good precipitation of the sucrate.

After trying several experiments it was found that the best precipitation of sucrose could be obtained by taking a 12 per cent. solution of sucrose and gradually stirring in a quantity of lime equal to the weight of sucrose taken, the stirring being mechanically continued for 4 hours at a temperature of 0—6°. The precipitate was collected and the filtrate was boiled and filtered until no more precipitate appeared. Sucrose was estimated in the final filtrate by the polarimeter.

(a). Temperature 0-6°; 30 g. sucrose, water and lime in proportion, 5.8 g. sucrose left in filtrate; 80.6 per cent. sucrose precipitated.

(b). Another 15 g. lime were stirred into the final filtrate of above, mixture filtered, etc., 4.8 g. sucrose left in filtrate; total sucrose precipitated=84 per cent.

Longer stirring did not improve matters and higher working temperatures gave low yields.

Destruction of Glucose by Boiling with Lime.

Several experiments were tried by boiling a mixture of sucrose and glucose in aqueous solution with lime

varying the quantity of lime and the duration of boiling. It was found that boiling the solution for 2 hours with a quantity of lime equal to the quantity of glucose in solution was sufficient to destroy the glucose almost completely, glucose left undestroyed in the solution after boiling with lime was estimated by Fehling's solution, the precipitate of cuprous oxide being collected and estimated by the volumetric permanganate method (Browne, "Hand book of Sugar Analysis," p. 410).

Twelve g. sucrose, 4 g. glucose, 3 g. lime, 100 c. c. water, boiled for 2 hours; 0.217 g. glucose left.

There is no appreciable destruction of sucrose by this treatment.

Recovery of Sucrose from a Mixture of Sucrose and Glucose.

Eight g. sucrose and 4 g. glucose were dissolved in 160 c. c. water (making a solution containing approximately the same quantities of sucrose and glucose as in molasses diluted to 12° Brix) and boiled with 3 g. lime for 2 hours. Then in the course of 3 hours 9 g. freshly burnt finely ground lime were gradually stirred in to the mixture at a temperature of 0°—10°. The solid was collected, the filtrate boiled etc., as in the experiments on the precipitation of sucrose. Sucrose in filtrate=0.718 g. (8.9 per cent. of sucrose taken); glucose in filtrate=0.025 g.

The cake was suspended in water and decomposed by carbonic acid.

Sucrose recovered from cake by 2½ hours' carbonation
=4.68 g.

Sucrose recovered by an extra 2 hours' carbonation
=1.52 g.

Total sucrose recovered from cake =6.20 g.

This is a recovery of 77.5 per cent. of sucrose in original mixture.

Recovery of Sucrose from Molasses.

Twenty g. molasses (containing 43 per cent. sucrose and about 20 per cent. glucose) were dissolved in 100 c. c. water and treated by the same process.

- (a) Sucrose in filtrate = 2.64 g. (30.7 per cent. of sucrose in molasses).
 Glucose „ = 0.028 g.
- (b) Sucrose in filtrate = 2.22 g. (25.8 per cent. of sucrose in molasses).
 Glucose „ = 0.018 g.
- (c) Sucrose in filtrate = 1.8 g. (20.9 per cent. of sucrose in molasses).

In the last experiment the cake was carbonated.

Sucrose recovered from cake = 5.7 g. (66.3 per cent. of sucrose in molasses).

The sucrose recovered was by no means colourless. The purity was calculated from the density of the sucrose solution and found to be 66 per cent.

Recovery of Sucrose from a Mixture of Sucrose and Glucose (repeated).

The low purity of the sucrose recovered from the molasses made it desirable to go back and repeat the experiment with a mixture of sucrose and glucose and determine the purity of the sucrose isolated. This had not been done in the previous experiment. The only modification was that the mixture was boiled with the lime for 4 instead of 2 hours.

Sucrose recovered from cake = 5.38 g. (67.2 per cent. of sucrose taken).

Glucose in product recovered from cake = 0.15 g.

Purity of recovered sucrose = 60.8 per cent.

Treatment of Glucose only by same Process.

It seemed possible that the low purity of the sucrose obtained by carbonating the cake might be due to the precipitation as insoluble lime compounds of the decomposition products from the glucose. To ascertain whether this was the case 4 g. of glucose only were put through the same process, but on carbonating the cake only 0.358 g. solid was obtained which is an insignificant quantity compared with the 3.5 g. of other solids which were mixed with the recovered sucrose in the last experiment.

*Attempt to Recover Sucrose of Higher Purity from a Mixture of Sucrose and Glucose.**(a) By washing the cake with hot water.*

The last experiment indicated that the impurities in the recovered sucrose were due to impurities retained mechanically or by adsorption in the lime sucrate cake. An attempt was made to remove these impurities by boiling the cake with 100 c. c. water and again filtering.

Sucrose recovered from washed cake = 0.39 g.

Sucrose in wash-water = 3.85 g.

This unexpected result showed that washing the cake, even with hot water, lowered the yield of sucrose to an extent to make the process technically useless. The result was unexpected because the solubility of tricalcium sucrate is recorded in the literature as 1 part in 200 parts boiling water and 1 part in 100 parts cold water so that not more than 0.5 g. tricalcium sucrate equivalent to about 0.33 g. sucrose was expected to be dissolved by the wash-water.

(b) By carbonating the mixture after the lime-boil and before precipitation of the lime sucrate.

Just as juice is purified by the carbonation process it was thought possible to remove the impurities by

carbonating after the lime-boil, filtering and rejecting the calcium carbonate, then cooling the filtrate, stirring in the rest of the lime to precipitate the lime sucrate, and proceeding as before.

(1) Sucrose recovered from cake = 4.68 g. (58.5 per cent. of sucrose taken).

Purity of recovered sucrose = 84.6 per cent.

(2) The carbonation, after the lime-boil, was carried out in two stages as in the factory process. The cake was also carbonated in two stages. The colour of the recovered sucrose was considerably improved.

Sucrose recovered from cake

by first carbonation = 2.15 g. (purity 83 per cent.)

Sucrose recovered from cake

by second carbonation = 2.91 g. (purity 98 per cent.)

Total sucrose recovered = 5.06 g. (63.2 per cent. of sucrose taken.)

It appears that with some sacrifice in yield the purity of the recovered sucrose can be considerably raised by carbonation after the lime-boil.

Attempt to Recover Sucrose of higher Purity from Molasses by Carbonating the Mixture after the Lime-boil and before Precipitation of the Lime Sucrate.

Twenty g. of molasses were treated.

(a) Sucrose recovered from cake = 3.95 g. (45.9 per cent. of sucrose in molasses).

Purity of recovered sucrose

(calculated from density of sucrose solution)*

= 60.2 per cent.

* Purity calculated from weight of total solids on evaporating sucrose solution.

Purity of recovered sucrose (calculated from weight of total solids left on evaporating sucrose solution) = 69.9 per cent.

Sucrose recovered from cake in two stages.

Sucrose recovered from first carbonation = 3.95 g. (purity 73.7 per cent).

Sucrose recovered from second carbonation = 0.26 g.

Total sucrose recovered = 4.21 g. (49 per cent. of sucrose in molasses).

This result with molasses is disappointing in comparison with that obtained with a mixture of sucrose and glucose both as regards yield and purity.

Calculation shows that unless a better yield and better purity can be obtained the process is commercially useless. Taking molasses at Rs. 2, sugar at Rs. 12, and quicklime at 12 as. per maund, and reckoning on a yield of crystalline sugar equal to 50 per cent. of the sugar in the molasses, we have

Cost of 100 md. molasses	Rs. 200
Cost of 60 md. lime	„ 45
		Rs. 245
Value of 20 md. sugar produced ...		Rs. 240

EXPERIMENTS TO INCREASE THE YIELD OF SUCROSES

(PERFORMED BY H. S. CHATURVEDI).

In the preliminary experiments the best precipitation of sucrose was 84 per cent., the best recovery of sucrose 77 per cent. whilst with molasses it was not much more than 50 per cent. Attempts were made to improve the precipitation.

Precipitation of Sucrose by Lime.

In repeating Mr. Gupta's experiments with pure sucrose solution the precipitation of sucrose was not so good as obtained by Mr. Gupta, the precipitation being about 60 per cent.

Attempts were made to improve the precipitation by using (a) freshly prepared cream of lime, (b) freshly burnt quick-lime which had been passed through a 100-mesh sieve but the results were still worse, precipitation being 38.5 per cent., and 41.5 per cent., respectively. Arguing that the insoluble lime sucrate might produce a coating round the particles of lime and prevent further action it was decided to stir in the lime in two instalments, filtering before the second addition. This gave very good results.

(1) Temperature 0° — 5° ; 12 g. sucrose in 100 c. c. water; 12 g. lime in 2 instalments; 0.61 g. sucrose left in solution; 95 per cent. sucrose precipitated.

(2) Temperature 0° — 5° ; 12 g. sucrose in 100 c. c. water; 12 g. lime in 2 instalments; 0.61 g. sucrose left in solution; 97.8 per cent. sucrose precipitated

Recovery of Sucrose from Molasses by Adding Lime in two Instalments.

Twenty g. of molasses were dissolved in 115 c.c. water, boiled with 3 g. lime for two hours and then cooled to $0-5^{\circ}$ and 9 g. lime added in two instalments.

(a). Sucrose in filtrate = 0.92 g.; 93 per cent. sucrose precipitated.

(b). Sucrose in filtrate = nil; 100 per cent. sucrose precipitated. Sucrose recovered from cake = 7.18 g. (83.7 per cent. of sucrose in molasses).

Purity of recovered sucrose

(total solids by weighing) = 70.5 per cent.

„ (total solids by density
of sucrose solution) = 65.6 per cent.

Recovery of Sucrose from Molasses, Carbonating after the Lime-boil and Precipitating Lime Sucrate by Adding Lime in two Instalments.

Twenty g. of molasses treated.

(a). Sucrose in filtrate = 0.88 g. (10.2 per cent. of sucrose in molasses).

Sucrose recovered from cake = 5.9 g. (68.6 per cent. of sucrose in molasses).

Purity (total solids by weighing) = 77 per cent.

„ (total solids by density of sucrose solution) = 70.6 per cent.

(b). Sucrose in filtrate = 1.3 g. (15.1 per cent. of sucrose in molasses).

Sucrose recovered from cake = 4.68 g. (54.4 per cent. of sucrose in molasses).

Purity (by weighing total solids) = 70.9 per cent.

The addition of lime in two instalments considerably increases the yield of sucrose but the process cannot be considered satisfactory because the purity of the recovered sucrose is low. It is remarkable that so large an amount of impurity is retained, mechanically or by adsorption by the lime sucrate; in the case where the sucrose recovered from the cake was 7.18 g. and the purity 70.5 per cent., about 3 g. of impurities were present in the precipitate.

EXPERIMENTS TO IMPROVE THE PURITY OF THE
RECOVERED SUCROSE

(PERFORMED BY H. S. CHATURVEDI).

In order to be sure that the low purity of the recovered sucrose is not due to the formation of an insoluble lime compound of the decomposition products of the glucose

the experiment was repeated in which glucose only was put through the process. From 4 g. of glucose only 0.36 g. total solids was recovered on carbonating the cake, confirming the previous experiment.

Purity of Sucrose Recovered from a Mixture of Sucrose and Sodium Chloride.

Sodium chloride was chosen as a simple crystalloid which would have little tendency to be adsorbed.

Eight g. of sucrose and 4 g. sodium chloride were dissolved in 100 c. c. water and treated with 12 g. lime in two instalments, precipitate being washed as in previous experiments.

Sucrose in filtrate	= 2.34 g.
Sucrose recovered from cake	= 4.94 g.
Purity of recovered sucrose (total solids by weighing)	= 85.9 per cent.
Purity of recovered sucrose (total solids by density of sucrose solution)	= 77.9 per cent.

This experiment shows that even a simple salt like common salt is retained by the precipitate to a considerable extent.

Recovery of Sucrose from a Mixture of Sucrose and Glucose, Washing the Lime Succrate Cake with Rectified Spirit.

Precipitate washed in original funnel with 100 c. c. cold rectified spirit.

Sucrose in original filtrate	= 1.14 g.
Sucrose recovered from cake	= 5.33 g.
Purity (by weighing total solids)	= 81.6 per cent.
Sucrose recovered from cake by second carbonation	= 0.26 g.

There is an improvement in purity but nothing considerable.

Recovery of Sucrose from a Mixture of Sucrose and Glucose, Washing the Lime Sucrate with boiling Water and Reprecipitating the Sucrose from the Wash-water.

In inorganic analysis a precipitate which is impure on account of adsorption is purified by re-dissolving and re-precipitating. It was decided to apply this process to the lime sucrate. The cake obtained in the usual way was mixed with 100 c. c. boiling water in a mortar and filtered; residue = ppt. (A).

The filtrate was boiled and filtered; residue = ppt. (B). The filtrate was cooled to 0-6° and 4.5 g. lime stirred in.

The solid was collected = ppt. (C). The filtrate is called the second filtrate.

PURITY.

I			II		
Sucrose in 1st filtrate,	0.70 g.		0.67 g.		
" ppt. (A)	1.09	82.2 p. c.	2.00	78.6 p. c.	
" ppt. (B)	2.00	92.7 p. c.	0.65	75.8 p. c.	
" ppt. (C)	1.04	86.1 p. c.	1.40	84.1 p. c.	
" 2nd filtrate,	0.65		0.88		
Sucrose in total carbonated cake =	2.60 g.				
Total sucrose accounted for	5.48		8.20		
III			IV		
Sucrose in 1st filtrate,	0.26 g.		1.10 g.		
" ppt. (A)	2.18	80.5 p. c.	2.96	79.6 p. c.	
" ppt. (B)	1.56	78.6 p. c.	0.88	81.5 p. c.	
" ppt. (C)	1.35	86.0 p. c.	0.62	91.2 p. c.	
" 2nd filtrate,	1.20		0.67		
" Total carbonated cake,	0.90		0.20		
Total sucrose accounted for	7.45		6.33		

In the first experiment there was a large proportion of sucrose unaccounted for. The second experiment indicated that this had been due to incomplete decomposition of the lime sucrate by carbonic acid. In the second and third experiments the lime sucrate was mixed with water and boiled whilst carbon dioxide was passed in. This made the decomposition of the lime sucrate more complete.

Recovery of Sucrose from Molasses, Washing the Lime Sucrate with boiling Water and Reprecipitating the Sucrose from the Wash-water.

Twenty g. of molasses were treated as above.

Sucrose in 1st filtrate	0.88 g.
in ppt. (A)	3.74 (purity, 73.7 p. c.)
,, in ppt. (B)	0.10 (,, 66.4 p. c.)
,, in ppt. (C)	1.23 (,, 80.6 p. c.)
,, 2nd filtrate	1.14
,, total carbonated cake	0.23
Total sucrose accounted for			<hr/> 7.32 g.

An increase of purity has been attained with considerable loss of yield. A yield of 59 per cent. sucrose with average purity of 75 per cent. is to be compared with 83.7 per cent. yield of purity 70.5 per cent. (without treatment of the cake). Obviously the increase in purity does not counterbalance the loss in yield.

Experiments to destroy the Glucose by other Methods with a View to Improve the Purity of the Recovered Sucrose.

It was thought that if the glucose was destroyed by caustic soda or by lime at lower temperature, the decomposition products, being different from those formed

by lime at the boil, might not be retained to the same extent by the lime sucrate.

Decomposition of Glucose by boiling with Caustic Soda Solution.

(a) Eight g. sucrose, 4 g. glucose, 0.8 g. caustic soda dissolved in 100 c.c. water and boiled for 1 hour; at the end of this time the solution was no longer alkaline; glucose left in solution = 1.92 g.

(b) Eight g. sucrose, 4 g. glucose, 1.5 g. caustic soda dissolved in 100 c.c. water, and boiled for 2 hours; the solution was alkaline and contained 0.49 g. glucose.

(c) Eight g. sucrose, 4 g. glucose, 1.5 g. caustic soda dissolved in 100 c.c. water, and boiled for 3 hours; 0.38 g. glucose left in solution.

Recovery of Sucrose from a Mixture of Sucrose and Glucose, Decomposing the Glucose by boiling with Caustic Soda.

The experiment was carried out as in (b) above, then the mixture was cooled to 0–6°, and 9 g. lime in two instalments were stirred in.

Sucrose in filtrate = 0.57 g.

Sucrose recovered from cake = 4.94 g.

Purity (total solids by weighing) = 80.1 per cent.

This result is not strikingly better than those obtained with lime.

Decomposition of Glucose by Lime at lower Temperatures.

(a) Eight g. sucrose, 4 g. glucose, 3 g. lime and 8 c.c. water were allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature for 42 hours; glucose left = 2.47 g.

(b) Eight g. sucrose, 4 g. glucose, 3 g. lime and 8 c.c. water were allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature

at 70° for 2 hours ; glucose left=0.28 g. ; colour of solution very dark.

(c) Eight g. sucrose, 4 g. glucose, 3 g. lime and 8 c.c. water were allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature at 70° for 4 hours ; glucose left=0.20 g. ; colour of solution very dark.

This is not a promising way of decomposing the glucose owing to the dark colour of the decomposition products.

Conclusion.

The results so far obtained have been collected together for publication, although it is obvious that success has not yet been attained in the solution of the problem. A striking feature of the results is their irregularity. The same experiment repeated never gives quite the same results and often the variation is considerable.

Perhaps the most puzzling feature is the solubility of the lime sucrate in boiling water, which is much greater than that recorded in the literature. The experiments on washing the lime sucrate with hot water gave most variable results. It seems as though the lime sucrate precipitated in the cold is not true tricalcium sucrate, and perhaps if the conditions could be found for a fairly complete precipitation of the true tricalcium sucrate the problem would be solved. The lime sucrate formed is gelatinous and therefore difficult to wash. If it could be obtained crystalline or at any rate not gelatinous it could probably be washed more easily.

But the results so far obtained are quite promising from the commercial standpoint. By the simplest process we have obtained a recovery of 84 per cent. of the sugar in molasses in the form of a syrup of 70 per cent. purity. If we assume that this syrup, on boiling, would give crystalline sugar and leave molasses of 40 per cent. purity

we could get 24 parts of crystalline sugar and 24 parts of molasses from 100 parts of molasses containing 40 per cent. sucrose. Taking the same prices for molasses and sugar as in our previous calculation we have—

100 md. of molasses	...	Rs. 200
60 md. of lime	„ 45
	Total	<u>Rs. 245</u>

Value of 24 md. sugar produced @ Rs. 12 per md.	Rs. 288
Value of 24 md. molasses produced „ 48
	<u>Total Rs. 336</u>

This leaves a considerable margin for working charges.

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